

Talk: Harnessing Microbial Power: Enzymatic Solutions for Bioplastics Recycling

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Abstract

The shift from conventional plastics to bioplastics is accelerating, driven by regulations and consumer demand. To remain competitive, companies must develop strategies that balance economic viability and sustainability, particularly regarding end-of-life solutions. With global bioplastics production expected to reach 2.98 million metric tons by 2027, waste management must evolve to support the efficient recycling of these materials.

Among the leading bioplastics, polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) stand out, with a projected 16.3% market growth by 2030.

However, maximizing their circularity requires advances in enzymatic recycling technologies. PHA degradation relies on PHA depolymerases, enzymes that remain underexplored despite their potential. These enzymes target either short-chain (scl-PHA) or medium-chain (mcl-PHA) polymers and function intracellularly or extracellularly, yet their kinetic mechanisms remain poorly understood.

Advancing enzymatic PHA recycling is key to closing the loop in bioplastic sustainability, reducing waste, and minimizing environmental impact. By unlocking the full potential of depolymerases, bioplastics can become a true pillar of the circular economy.

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ReBioCycle

ReBioCycle: A new European blueprint for circular bioplastics upcycling solutions

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